

Homœopathic pharmacy—education, research and optimism

Over the least 20 years, the importance of homœopathic pharmacy has become more apparent. This is in marked contrast to its status during the days of Samuel Hahnemann who recommended to his medical colleagues that they should prepare their own medicines because contemporary compounders and dispensers could not be trusted!

If it had not been for legal moves made by 2 pharmacists in the early 1970s with the financial support of the British Homœopathic Association (BHA) to protect the 'special' manufacturing services that produce isopathic remedies and nosodes, these products might have disappeared altogether. Since then, pharmacists from the manufacturers have been working hard in this country, and alongside European colleagues, to conclude fair and workable licensing regulations that reflect the special nature of homœopathic medicines. Their patience is about to be rewarded with ratification of the recently agreed EC directives by the UK Parliament. The new *British Homœopathic Pharmacopoeia* will appear soon. Drawing heavily on its German counterpart, it standardizes many of the common processes used in this country, and is the result of intense activity.

Debate

Most UK community pharmacists involved in the supply of homœopathic medicines have adopted a reactive approach, seeking to satisfy an over-the-counter (OTC) demand from the public that has intensified over recent years. There has been a similar increase in the number of homœopathic prescriptions pre-

sented by patients. Although significant progress is being made, a look at the market in other EC countries shows that we still have a considerable way to go. This demand is being generated by a number of factors including fear of conventional drug side effects, general dissatisfaction with existing therapies and low cost. These and other likely reasons were discussed in an article in the *Pharmaceutical Journal* in November 1991, provoking a lively correspondence that continued for more than 18 months.

The British Pharmaceutical Conference in 1992 debated whether pharmacists should be involved with the promotion of homœopathic medicines and concluded that they should by a huge majority. The sceptics did not come up with anything new, most criticisms being based solely on the lack of scientific evidence. It was a measure of their bias that speakers chose to ignore the evidence that is available, including Reilly's much-quoted hayfever trials and Day's veterinary work. Their preoccupation with the necessity of providing explanations for homœopathic mechanisms was understandable, for the Pharmacists' Code of Ethics precludes the supply of any product if there is reason to doubt its efficacy, and this is often linked to scientific considerations. Why is it that this troubles so many colleagues on this side of the Channel, yet does not seem to trouble the French or Germans? Further, such requirements do not seem to apply to various conventional preparations, including antitussives, that have been counter prescribed for years, despite doubtful efficacy. A case of double standards?

Education

The journal *Chemist and Druggist* has also featured educational articles and correspondence on homœopathy. The demand for speakers on homœopathy at Royal Pharmaceutical Society Branch Meetings has rocketed. This demonstrates that there is clearly an increasing willingness to discuss homœopathy amongst 'conventional' pharmacists. Such interest from both the profession and the public led to an urgent requirement to provide standardized education. The new national Faculty of Homœopathy Certificate in Basic Homœopathic Pharmacy is proving extremely popular, attracting considerable interest from home and abroad. Many excellent courses have been offered in the past—notably by the BHA and the manufacturers—but the Faculty course provides a co-ordinated curriculum for the first time. Intermediate and advanced courses will follow, the establishment of a Diploma of PharmMFHom qualification being the ultimate goal. Even more significantly, professional interest has prompted the National Pharmaceutical Association to commission a distance learning pack on homœopathic pharmacy, and this will be available to all community pharmacists throughout the UK in the near future. A study published in the July issue of the *British Homœopathic Journal* shows that over half the 16 schools of pharmacy in the UK give their students some exposure to complementary medicine; the others are being encouraged to follow suit. The problem of pharmacy assistant training is also being addressed. An important chain of high-street pharmacies has recently provided elementary training in homœopathy for 500 of its pharmacists.

As a bigger pool of well-informed, standardized knowledge is built up in pharmacies, correct dispensing techniques will be adopted, with greater awareness of contamination risks and counselling needs. Further, the OTC approach should become proactive, poly-chrests being added to the pharmacists' armamentarium for the treatment of first-aid or simple self-limiting acute conditions that currently lie within the limits of conventional competency. It has to be acknowledged that in most busy conventional pharmacies the feasibility of giving classical or constitutional advice to patients is limited. It is to be hoped, however, that homœopathic OTC medicines will be offered routinely to 'at risk' categories—the

pregnant, the elderly, the young and where interaction with prescribed conventional drugs is a possibility. This will raise the awareness of homœopathy in the eyes of the public and reduce the influence of health stores.

Research

The research road is being followed more slowly, although several papers have been published by independent workers in the last 2 years. The manufacturers are notable by their absence in this area. Funding for others—yes, but practical pharmacy research—no! There are huge areas within the practice of homœopathic pharmacy that urgently need investigation. The establishment of reliable methods for monitoring the purity and stability of mother tinctures would be an important advance in satisfying new regulations; some work has been carried out in this field. A search for new medicines would surely yield results. A lack of human and financial resources is hampering progress at present. Pharmacy initiatives deserve to be encouraged and supported by funds set aside for the purpose by the Homœopathic Medical Research Council.

The work which has been done has not been carried out in a vacuum. Useful contacts have been made and help given to pharmacy colleagues in New Zealand, Russia, Ireland and on European and international committees.

In a recent survey 3 times as many respondents said that they had heard about homœopathy through their local pharmacy than through their GP. Given the accessibility of premises, increased knowledge and an acceptance that patient choice must be respected, the opportunities for promoting homœopathy through community pharmacies have never been better.

Traditionally pharmacists have been involved 'behind the scenes', supporting colleagues in other homœopathic disciplines. The time has now come for a more visible role to be taken within the health care team. With a firm, expanding educational infrastructure, an embryonic research base and new licensing regulations for our manufacturers, the foundations of a higher profile for homœopathic pharmacy have been laid. Homœopathy as a whole should be proud of what pharmacy has achieved. The future may indeed be viewed with considerable optimism.

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